

Knowledge on Coronary Artery Disease among adults people in community at Biratnagar

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Abstract: Coronary artery disease (CAD) is characterized by the accumulation of plaque within the layers of coronary arteries. It is the leading cause of death globally and is affecting developing countries as well. The study entitled “Knowledge on Coronary Artery Disease among Adults in Community” was conducted with the main objective to assess knowledge on coronary artery disease among adults. The study was descriptive in nature in which non-probability purposive sampling has been used for data collection. Sixty-nine respondents were interviewed through semi-structured questions. Out of 69 respondents, 33.3% were from 30-39 years age group, and the mean age was 39.17. Similarly, 56.5% were male and 39.1% were from Brahmin ethnicity. Likewise, 37.7% of the respondents had the qualification of secondary education, 24.6% were engaged in services at various government and non-government organizations. Similarly, 55.1% of the respondents identified a high cholesterol diet as risk factors of coronary artery disease. Moreover, the findings of the study revealed that 58.0% of the respondents have inadequate knowledge and 42.0% have adequate knowledge of coronary artery disease. This study showed a significant relationship between the level of knowledge and education ($p=0.019$) whereas the other independent variables had no statistical significance with the level of knowledge. This study concluded that knowledge of coronary artery disease was found to be inadequate.

Keywords: Coronary artery disease, knowledge of CAD, Birat, etc.

Introduction:

Coronary artery disease (CAD) is characterized by the accumulation of plaque within the layers of the coronary arteries. The acute coronary syndrome is an umbrella term that is used to describe many of the complications associated with coronary artery disease. These include stroke, unstable angina, non-ST elevation myocardial infarction, and ST-elevation myocardial infarction (Nettina, 2012).

CAD is the leading cause of death globally and one of the major health burdens worldwide. Atherosclerotic changes begin at an early age and progress to great extent during adolescence. Many risk factors have been associated with coronary artery diseases which are mainly of modifiable risk factors like smoking, dyslipidemia, hypertension, diabetes mellitus, obesity, physical inactivity, unhealthy habits, eating fast foods, stress, and non-modifiable risk factors include age, gender, the family history which make today's adolescents vulnerable to coronary artery disease (Smeltzer et al., 2011).

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CAD is responsible for nearly half of all deaths in the developed world and is expected to be the world's number one cause of death or disability by the year 2020. Cardiovascular diseases are the number one cause of death globally. An estimated 17.5 million people died from cardiovascular diseases in 2012, representing 31% of all global deaths. Of these deaths, an estimated 7.4 million were due to coronary heart disease and 6.7 million were due to stroke (WHO, 2016).

Several countries like the US, Canada, Argentina, UK, and Ireland have reported a more than 60% decline in coronary artery death rates in the past 30 years. Approximately 60 to 70% of the decline is due to the reduction in the incidence of a heart attack from improvements in risk factors. The lifestyle habits that can help treat coronary artery disease can also help prevent it from developing in the first place. Leading a healthy lifestyle like no smoking, controlling conditions such as high blood pressure, high cholesterol, and diabetes, staying physically active, eating healthy foods, *maintaining* a healthy weight, and reducing and managing stress can help keep arteries strong, elastic and smooth and allow for the maximum blood flow (Kaur, 2016).

A cross-sectional study conducted to identify the hospital-based prevalence of noncommunicable diseases in Kathmandu tertiary level hospital found that in Nepal, noncommunicable disease account for more than 44 % of deaths and 80 % of outpatient contacts. Nearly one-third of the population has hypertension, 15 % has diabetes, chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases 43 % are the most common NCDs among outpatients followed by cardiovascular disease 40 %. Furthermore, earlier studies have reported a higher level of alcohol and tobacco use in Nepal contributing to shifting disease patterns in Nepal (Bhandari, et al., 2014). Another study conducted on Cardiovascular Health Knowledge, Attitude and Practice in urbanizing community in Jhaukhel-Duwakot of Bhaktapur district among 777 adult's participants concluded that 44% of respondents had insufficient knowledge and less than 20% had highly satisfactory knowledge on heart disease (Vaidya et al., 2011).

Methodology

A community based descriptive cross-sectional research design was conducted at Madhumara-8 in Biratnagar, Morang. The study population was both male and female of 21-65years of age who were willing to participate in the study. A non-probability purposive sampling technique was used to select the respondents. The total sample size was 69 and the duration of the study was only two weeks. The data collection was done through the semi-structured interview schedule. The instrument was divided into two parts, part I consisted of socio-demographic information, and part II consisted of questions related to coronary artery disease. All together 8 questions were related knowledge. Each correct response was scored 1 and in case of multiple responses, each correct response carried 1 score. Question number 2, 4, 7, and 9 were excluded while calculating the knowledge score. The total score of the knowledge related questionnaire was 26. The level of knowledge was categorized as adequate and inadequate knowledge on the basis of the median score:

Adequate knowledge: more than or equal to median (≥ 13).

Inadequate knowledge: less than median (≤ 12).

Verbal consent was taken after explaining the purpose and its risk and benefits prior to the interview from each respondent. All the collected data were checked for error, accuracy, and

completeness. Data were edited, coded, and analyzed using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 20.0. In descriptive analysis percentage, frequency, mean, median, and standard deviation were used to analyze demographic data. Inferential statistics i.e. chi-square test was used to find out the association between knowledge and selected demographic variables and findings was presented on tabular forms.

Findings:

The mean age of respondents was 39.17 years with most of the respondents (33.3%) belong to the age group 30-39 years. more than half of the respondents (56.5%) were male. Similarly, 39.1% of the respondents were from the Brahmin ethnic group. Likewise, more than half of the respondents (79.7%) had no family history of coronary artery disease.

Table 1: Socio-demographic profile of the study (n=69)

Variables	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Age		
20-29	15	21.7
30-39	23	33.3
40-49	15	21.7
50-59	8	11.6
60 above	8	11.6
Mean ± SD 39.17±12.288		
Sex		
Male	39	56.5
Female	30	43.5
Ethnicity		
Brahmin	27	39.1
Chhetri	14	20.3
Madeshi	14	20.3
Janajati	14	20.3
Family history of coronary artery disease		
Yes	14	20.3
No	55	79.7

Knowledge on Coronary Artery Disease (CAD):

The study result shows that 43.5% of the respondents correctly answered the meaning of coronary artery disease. In concern to the source of information, 31.9% of respondents stated friends as the main source of information about coronary artery disease. Table 2 represents that more than half of the respondents (55.1%) answered high cholesterol diet as a risk factor of coronary artery disease followed by obesity 49.3% and 2.9% of the respondents answered sex as a risk factor respectively. Likewise, 56.5% of the respondents answered shortness of breath as symptoms of coronary artery disease.

Table 2: Knowledge on Risk factors and Sign and Symptoms of Coronary Artery Disease (n=69)

Variables ²	Frequency(f)	Percentage (%)
Risk Factors of CAD		
Age	23	33.3
Sex	2	2.9
Hereditary	26	37.7
Smoking	26	37.7
High cholesterol diet	38	55.1
Physical inactivity	4	5.8
Obesity	34	49.3
High blood pressure	19	27.5
Stress	17	24.6
Sign and Symptoms		
Shortness of breath	39	56.5
Chest pain	36	52.2
Excessive sweating	14	20.3
Fainting	5	7.2

Table 3 below shows that 100% of the respondents stated coronary artery disease can be prevented. Among them, 73.9% and 43.5% answered eating low cholesterol diet and maintaining weight as preventive measures of coronary artery disease respectively while 18.8% of the respondents answered maintaining blood pressure as preventive measures of coronary artery disease.

Table 3: Knowledge on Prevention of Coronary Artery Disease (n=69)

Variables ³	Frequency(f)	Percentage (%)
CAD is preventable		
Yes	69	100
Preventive measures		
Eating low cholesterol diet	51	73.9
Maintaining weight	30	43.5
Regular exercise	28	40.6
Quitting smoking	28	40.6
Avoiding stress	19	27.5
Regular health checkup	19	27.5
Maintain blood pressure	13	18.8

Table 4 shows that 100% of the respondents answered coronary artery disease is treatable. Among them, 79.7% of the respondents answered taking medication is the treatment measure of coronary artery disease. Similarly, 88.4% of the respondents stated that compliance of drug is important for treating coronary artery disease. Table 5 reveals that 58.0% of the respondents have inadequate knowledge on coronary artery disease and 42.0% have adequate knowledge.

² Multiple response questions, each response is considered 100%.

³ Multiple response questions, each response is considered as 100%.

Table 4: Knowledge on Treatment of Coronary Artery Disease (n=69)

Variables	Frequency(f)	Percentage (%)
CAD is treatable		
Yes	69	100
Treatment measures⁴		
Medication	55	79.7
Surgery	16	23.2
Need for drug compliance		
Yes	61	88.4
No	8	11.6

Table 5: Level of Knowledge on Coronary Artery Disease (n=69)

Knowledge level	Frequency(f)	Percentage (%)
Adequate knowledge	29	42.0
Inadequate knowledge	40	58.0

Table 6: Association between level of knowledge and selected demographic variables (n=69)

Variable	Level of knowledge		p-value ⁵
	Adequate (%)	Inadequate (%)	
Age			
< 39	13 (18.8%)	25 (36.2%)	0.145
> 40	16 (23.2%)	15 (21.7%)	
Sex			
Male	15 (21.7%)	24 (34.8%)	0.494
Female	14 (20.3%)	16 (23.2%)	
Education			
Literate	29 (42.0%)	33 (47.8%)	0.019*
Illiterate	0 (0.0%)	7 (10.1%)	
Occupation			
Service	16 (23.2%)	25 (36.2%)	0.541
Non-service	13 (18.8%)	15 (21.7%)	

Table 6 shows the association of level of knowledge with selected demographic variables. The result shows that there was significant association between level of knowledge and education status ($p=0.019$) whereas the other independent variables had no statistical significance with level of knowledge ($p> 0.05$).

Discussion:

The study's demographic findings revealed that among 69 respondents mean age was 39.17 and more than half of the respondents (56.5%) were male which is similar to the findings of a descriptive cross-sectional study conducted in Turkey among 300 participants which showed that

⁴ Multiple response questions, each response is considered as 100%.

⁵ significant<0.05

the mean age was 34.58 and 53.3% of the respondents were male (Andsoy et al., 2015). A cross-sectional study conducted in AIMS among 217 adult participants showed that (57%) of the participants identified a high cholesterol diet as a risk factor of CAD (Saeed, O et al., 2009). The findings of this study revealed that the most identified risk factor was the high cholesterol diet 55.1% which added additional support to the result of this study. This study finding showed that more than half of the respondents (56.5%) cited shortness of breath as symptoms of CAD. This result is supported by a cross-sectional study conducted in Bhaktapur district among 405 adult populations showed that (57.8%) of the respondents identified shortness of breath as symptoms of CAD (Pande & Khadka, 2012).

The result of this study revealed that regarding preventability of CAD most of the respondents (73.9%) cited eating low cholesterol diet prevents heart disease which is similar to the study conducted in Bhaktapur district among 405 adult population showed that the majority (80.7%) identified decreasing fatty diet as preventive measures of heart disease (Pandey & Khadka, 2012). This study finding showed that among 69 respondents (58.0%) have inadequate knowledge of CAD, which is similar to a descriptive cross-sectional study conducted in Oman among 130 adult population which showed that (60.5%) have inadequate knowledge on CAD (Ammouri et al., 2016). The study's findings showed a significant association between the level of knowledge and education status of the respondents ($p=0.019$). This result is supported by a study conducted on Knowledge on Preventive Measures of Coronary Artery Disease among 405 adult population in Bhaktapur which showed a significant association between level of knowledge and education $p=0.000$ (Pandey & Khadka, 2012).

Conclusion :

The findings of this study revealed that the level of knowledge on coronary artery disease was found to be inadequate. Similarly, most of the respondents identified a high cholesterol diet as a risk factor of coronary artery disease. There was a significant association between level of knowledge and education whereas the other independent variables had no statistical significance with the level of knowledge.

Acknowledgements:

The authors would like to thank all the respondents of Madhumara, of Biratnagar who participated in this study. They are also thankful to Biratnagar Nursing Campus for proving the opportunity for study.

Ethical Approval Statement:

No patient of the disease under discussion was observed or interviewed during this study. As the study was based on the knowledge possessed by the common individuals, therefore, only interviews were conducted and the data extracted was analyzed.

Funding Information:

The study was not sponsored by any organization or the institution. No funding was provided by any individual or institution for the conduct of this study. Therefore, all expenses occurred were those by the researchers.

Competing Interest Declaration:

The authors have no conflict of interest or competing interest with any individual, organization or institute. The study was based only for the purpose of assessing the awareness of a particular disease among common people.

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